

Effect of Lime and Organic Matter Additions on Inorganic N-Transformation in Soil

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Comparatively higher amount of clay-fixed ammonium and lower amount of exchangeable ammonium were observed in the limed over the unlimed soil. Whereas, much lower amount of clay-fixed ammonium was observed in the starch added limed than in the corresponding unlimed soil. Irrespective of liming, magnitude of fixed ammonium in the starch added soil was much less than either the rice straw or no organic matter treated soil. It is suggested that the heterotrophic microbes utilised a considerable amount of fixed ammonium from the soil resulting a decrease in its amount under limed condition.

LIMING, soils of acidic reaction has been reported to increase mineralisation of nitrogen^{1,2}. Since there exists an equilibrium between exchangeable NH_4^+ and fixed NH_4^+ in soil³, part of the mineralised NH_4^+ may be converted to fixed form. Addition of easily decomposable organic matters of wide C/N ratio to soil increase the microbial activity in the soil. Microbial utilisation of available nitrogen creates a N-stress situation in soil, which is an environment conducive for the release of some fixed NH_4^+ -N³. These basic organic matter-linked processes get support from many other investigations^{4,5}.

In view of the facts stated above, it is expected that liming soils of acidic reaction would considerably influence the amount of clay-fixed NH_4^+ -N. Moreover, the mineralised NH_4^+ can also serve as a source for clay-fixed NH_4^+ . Since, the processes are appreciably influenced by microbial activity of the soil system, considerable variation between unlimed and limed soil is expected.

The present investigation has, therefore, been conducted to study the effect of liming soils of acidic reaction on changes in the amount of some important mineral forms of nitrogen including fixed NH_4^+ -N in system fertilised with and without inorganic NH_4^+ -N source and treated with and without organic matters of varying decomposibility and C/N ratio.

Experimental

The soil selected for present investigation was collected from the surface (0-15 cm) layer of Bagdubi village in Midnapore, West Bengal; pH, 5.4; organic C, 0.55%; total N, 0.071%; W.H.C., 51%; C.E.C., 7.84 me/100 g; clay, 39%; dominant clay mineral, illite; exchangeable NH_4^+ , 35; soluble NO_3^- , 14; fixed NH_4^+ , 514; NH_4^+ -fixing capacity of soil, 1079 ppm. According to U.S.D.A. system of classification, the soil belongs to plinthustalfs.

After collection, the soil was air-dried and crushed to pass through 0.5 mm sieve.

Liming soil of acidic reaction preceded the actual incubation experiment. The following procedure adopted for liming operation. The amount of lime equivalent to lime requirement was added to the soil. The lime was allowed to react for 3 months with repeated cycles of alternate wetting followed by air-drying. The corresponding unlimed soil was also subjected to the same process of alternate wetting and drying cycles.

Thus prepared unlimed and limed soils were incubated with the following treatments.

- (i) Control, where no source of nitrogen and organic matter was added.
- (ii) Starch was added at the rate of 0.5% of the soil (w/w).
- (iii) Rice straw (N, 1.20%) was added at the rate of 1% of the soil (w/w).
- (iv) Treatment (i) + 400 ppm N added through $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$.
- (v) Treatment (ii) + 400 ppm N added through $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$.
- (vi) Treatment (iii) + 400 ppm N added through $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$.

Duplicate samples of each of the treated soil were taken in 100 ml beakers. The soil was moistened to 50% of its W.H.C. by the addition of calculated amount of distilled water. Then the soils were allowed to incubate at laboratory temperature ($30 \pm 2^\circ$). Any loss in soil moisture due to evaporation was replenished on every alternate day by the addition of distilled water by difference in weight.

The soil samples were identically collected at two stages corresponding to 5th. and 15th. day of incubation. At each stage, the treated soil samples were analysed for exchangeable ammonium, soluble nitrate and fixed ammonium nitrogen. A 2 M KCl

solution was employed for the extraction of exchangeable ammonium and soluble nitrate nitrogen and estimated according to the method of Bremner and Keeney⁶. Fixed ammonium nitrogen was determined on the air-dried and ground NH_4 -free soil residue, from exchangeable- NH_4^+ determinations by the method of Silva and Bremner⁷. The procedure was considered essential for fixed NH_4^+ -N analysis in the laboratory incubation experiments, since air-drying in presence of NH_4 -N greatly increases fixation in this soil.

Results and Discussion

Perusal of the data (Table 1) reveals two interesting observations with respect to the amount of N in the available forms, namely exchangeable NH_4^+ -N and NO_3^- -N in the soil. Liming soils of acidic reaction resulted a decrease in the amount of exchangeable NH_4^+ -N in both the organic matter untreated and rice straw treated soils. This effect was noticed in the analyses of samples collected on both the 5th. and 15th. day stages of incubation. Secondly, the amount of decrease was found to be more marked in the organic matter untreated than the corresponding treated system. Besides, raising pH of the system, liming soils of acidic reaction, results in the increase of microbial activity in the soil. In the absence of added N, possibly the metabolic requirement of the increased microbial population was considerably met from the recently mineralised available N in the limed soil. Hence, comparatively higher amount of immobilisation of readily available nitrogen by the increased microbial activity in the limed than the corresponding unlimed soil was observed. This may explain the presence of lower concentration of exchangeable NH_4^+ -N in limed soil. The same logic may also explain the second observation. An almost similar observation was also reported by Nommik⁸ where no source of organic matter was added, the difference in the amount of available N between the limed and the unlimed soil was considerably higher than the corresponding values between the organic matter treated soil. It is a well known fact that in presence of ready source of carbonaceous material, the soil microbes multiply at a faster rate utilising the energy source. However, in the process, they also need some amount of nitrogen to meet their metabolic requirement. For this, naturally, the microbes would explore all possible sources of N in the soil. This was possibly the situation in the limed, organic matter added soil which was not treated with any source of inorganic nitrogen. Under these circumstances, the rapidly multiplied soil microbes utilised the recently mineralised forms of NH_4^+ and NO_3^- -N, thereby, causing more decrease in the amount of available nitrogen in the limed than the corresponding unlimed soil.

Irrespective of organic matter treatments, much higher amount of clay fixed NH_4^+ -N was observed in the limed than the corresponding unlimed soil

in the samples collected on the 5th. day of incubation. This trend of result was also observed on the 15th. day stage of sampling except in the starch added system, where the amount in the limed soil was less than the corresponding unlimed soil. During the three months reaction period following the addition of lime, with alternate wetting and drying cycles allowed, much higher amount of N-mineralisation from the native soil organic matter likely to have occurred in the limed than unlimed system. A part of the mineralised NH_4^+ might have been converted to fixed form, resulting in its higher concentration in the limed over the unlimed soil. But the lesser amount of fixed NH_4 observed on the 15th. day stage in the starch added limed soil than the other treatments was due to the easy decomposibility and a large carbon source of the added starch. Under such a N-starved condition, microbes might have utilised a considerable amount of fixed NH_4^+ -N from the soil for meeting their metabolic activity. This possibly resulted a decrease in the amount of fixed NH_4^+ -N in the limed soil.

For obvious reasons, in an arable soil, soluble NO_3^- -N fraction is present in smaller amount than the exchangeable NH_4^+ -N. Similar is the observation in the present investigation. Because of its small value, the change in the amount of NO_3^- -N due to liming, N-fertilisation and organic matter additions was not found to be as prominent as in the case of exchangeable NH_4^+ -N form on both the 5th. and 15th. day stages of sampling (Tables 1 and 2).

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF TWO SOURCES OF ADDED ORGANIC MATTER ON CHANGES IN THE AMOUNT (ppm) OF MINERAL FORMS OF N DURING INCUBATION OF LIMED AND UNLIMED SOIL

Organic matter treatment	Lime treatment	Amount of the forms of mineral nitrogen in soil					
		5th. day			15th. day		
		Exch. NH_4	Soluble NO_3	Fixed NH_4	Exch. NH_4	Soluble NO_3	Fixed NH_4
Control	Unlimed	88	14	523	61	7	506
	Limed	40	14	573	34	14	540
Starch	Unlimed	27	14	506	34	7	489
	Limed	27	7	523	34	7	455
Rice straw	Unlimed	40	14	523	40	7	506
	Limed	34	7	573	34	7	540

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF TWO SOURCES OF ADDED ORGANIC MATTER ON CHANGES IN THE AMOUNT (ppm) OF MINERAL FORMS OF N DURING INCUBATION OF LIMED AND UNLIMED SOIL DUE TO 400 ppm N ADDITION AS $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$

Organic matter treated	Lime treatment	Amount of the forms of mineral nitrogen in soil					
		5th. Day			15th. day		
		Exch. NH_4	Soluble NO_3	Fixed NH_4	Exch. NH_4	Soluble NO_3	Fixed NH_4
Control	Unlimed	371	0	50	384	7	34
	Limed	304	0	51	216	53	33
Starch	Unlimed	249	0	50	330	7	17
	Limed	122	6	-73	0	7	-51
Rice straw	Unlimed	344	0	50	303	7	34
	Limed	194	13	51	0	7	33

Analyses of the results, presented in Table 2 clearly show that on the 5th. day after its application, relatively higher proportion of the inorganic nitrogen was observed in exchangeable NH_4^+-N form in the unlimed than the corresponding limed soil. This observation was found to be equally valid under both the organic matter treated and untreated system. While 371 ppm of the added N was observed as exchangeable NH_4^+-N in the organic matter untreated soil, 344 and 249 ppm were recorded in the rice straw and starch added systems, respectively. Relatively smaller amount of 304, 194, 122 ppm were, however, recorded in the corresponding limed soil. Most likely, this is an effect of increased microbial utilisation of the added ammonium under limed situation. It was of further interest to note that the difference in the amount of exchangeable NH_4^+-N between the limed and the corresponding unlimed soil widened with increase in the period of incubation upto the 15th. day. Although considerable effect of liming soils of acidic reaction was noted in the amount of fixed ammonium in the unfertilised soil (Table 1), no such effect of liming could be detected in the corresponding

ammonium fertilised soil (Table 2). These results are in agreement with those reported earlier^{8,9-10}.

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References

1. A. H. CORNFIELD, *J. Sci. Food Agric.*, 1952, 3, 343.
2. M. NYBORG and P. B. HYOT, *Can. J. Soil Sci.*, 1978, 58, 331.
3. H. NOMMIK, *Acta Agric. Scand.*, 1957, 7, 395.
4. B. N. NAIK and D. K. BALLAL, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1968, 16, 155.
5. M. ADHIKARI and T. K. GANGULY, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1971, 19, 375.
6. J. M. BREMNER and D. R. KEENEY, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. Proc.*, 1966, 30, 577.
7. J. A. SILVA and J. M. BREMNER, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. Proc.*, 1966, 30, 587.
8. L. WIKLANDER, *Soil Sci.*, 1950, 69, 261.
9. T. HARADA and K. KUTSUNA, *Bull. Nat. Inst. Agric. Sci. Jpn. Ser.*, 1954, 3, 17.
10. G. S. N. RAJU and A. K. MUKHOPADHYAY, *Bull. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1976, 11, 174.